

Visceral Fat Markers in Psoriasis: A Cross-Sectional Analytical Study

S. Ragul¹, K. Gopalakrishnan², M. Bandhala Rajan³

¹Postgraduate, Department of Dermatology, Venereology and Leprology, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu, India

²Professor and Head of the Department of Dermatology, Venereology and Leprology, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu, India

³Assistant Professor, Department of Dermatology, Venereology and Leprology, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. K. Gopalakrishnan

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Abstract:

Background: Psoriasis is commonly linked to specific elements of metabolic syndrome, including hypertension, dyslipidemia, insulin resistance, and obesity. Conventional anthropometric measurements of obesity, including waist circumference (WC) or body mass index (BMI), fail to distinguish among subcutaneous fat versus visceral fat. However, it is important to note that visceral fat is linked to cardiovascular risk factors. This study aims to evaluate the levels of visceral fat markers, such as the Lipid accumulation product (LAP) index, Visceral adiposity index (VAI), and Plasma Atherogenicity Index (PAI), in individuals with psoriasis.

Methods: This study was conducted with 40 patients diagnosed with psoriasis, using a prospective cross-sectional design. Patient history, including demographic data, was gathered. The disease's severity was evaluated by computing the Psoriasis Area Severity Index (PASI). Along with other relevant investigations, a fasting lipid profile was completed. In addition, the LAP, VAI, and PAI indices were calculated using the relevant formulas and the outcomes were documented

Results: 18 (45%) were males and 22 (55%) were females. The mean (SD) age of the patients was 44.77 (7.02). Mean (SD) LAP was 190.82 (94.21), VAI was 5.16 (1.59) and PAI was 0.48 (0.14). The moderate-to-severe psoriasis group had a statistically significant ($p=0.0065$) higher LAP index (230.21 ± 91.1) than the mild psoriasis group (151.43 ± 81.56).

Conclusion: The LAP index, VAI, and PAI estimates can be suggested as a possible biomarker for early detection of cardiometabolic diseases that are common in people with psoriasis.

Keywords: Visceral Adiposity Index, Cardiometabolic Risk, Psoriasis, Central Obesity.

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Introduction

Psoriasis is a dermatological condition characterized by the presence of red papules and plaques on the skin. [1] These lesions can be found in specific areas or spread throughout the body, and they are well-defined, typically appearing in a symmetrical pattern. Additionally, the affected areas are often coated with white or silver scales. It has an equal impact on both males and females. [2] Onset occurs before the age of 46 in 75% of patients. The global prevalence of this condition varies from 0.5% to 11.4% and in India, it is 0.44 to 2.8%. [3]

Psoriasis patients exhibit an elevated cardiovascular risk. Psoriatic inflammation, systemic treatments, smoking, alcohol use, and metabolic syndrome are believed to raise the risk of cardiovascular disease. [4] An analysis of both national and international literature revealed a rise in the occurrence of metabolic syndrome among individuals with psoriasis. [5] Furthermore, it was discovered

that psoriasis is associated with hypertension, dyslipidaemia, high fasting blood glucose/insulin resistance, and obesity, independent of metabolic syndrome. [6] It was established that there is a direct correlation between the severity of the condition and the level of risk. Additionally, there have been studies indicating that young individuals with severe psoriasis have an elevated risk of myocardial infarction, which is comparable to the risk observed in the general population. [7]

Currently, obesity is a widespread and severe health issue that is considered the fifth leading cause of death worldwide. While the specific numbers may range across various research, it has been documented that more than 50% of individuals with psoriasis are affected by obesity. Historically, anthropometric measurements such as waist circumference (WC) as well as body mass index (BMI) have been employed as indicators of obesity.

[8]

Central obesity, which includes both visceral fat and subcutaneous fat, is linked to more severe metabolic disruptions in comparison to general obesity. Visceral fat, one of the two components of central obesity, has been linked to metabolic syndrome including cardiovascular illnesses. [9] Anthropometric measurements, such as waist circumference (WC) and body mass index (BMI), are unable to distinguish between visceral fat and subcutaneous fat. [9] Computed tomography (CT) along with body fat analyzers have been utilized to measure visceral fat in psoriasis; nevertheless, they are costly and not readily accessible. Therefore, there is a need for a straightforward and easily calculated index of visceral obesity to more effectively measure obesity amongst psoriasis patients. [10]

Research has demonstrated that the lipid accumulation product (LAP) index as well as visceral adiposity index (VAI) are effective in predicting insulin resistance and cardiometabolic risk factors in different diseases and in the general population. [11] These indices serve as indicators of dysfunction in visceral adipose tissue. The plasma atherogenic index (PAI) is a straightforward and easily computed measure that indicates the likelihood of developing coronary atherosclerosis. It has been proposed that a PAI value of less than 0.1 is associated with a low risk, a value between 0.1 and 0.24 is associated with a moderate risk, and a value greater than 0.24 is associated with a high risk. [12]

Aim

The aim of this study is to assess the levels of visceral fat markers, including the Lipid accumulation product (LAP) index, Visceral adiposity index (VAI), and Plasma Atherogenicity Index (PAI), in psoriasis patients.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Participants: This prospective cross sectional study evaluated the levels of visceral fat markers like LAP index, VAI and PAI in psoriatic patients. Trial protocol was approved by the institutional ethical committee. Patients above 18 years of age with new onset of psoriasis or old psoriasis patients were included in the study. Patients with known heart disease, known diabetes, systemic hypertension or patients on treatment for dyslipidemia were excluded from the study.

Recruitment: A previous study conducted by Satyaki Ganguly et al (2018) revealed that the average \pm standard deviation (SD) value of LAP in healthy subjects was 23.79 ± 13.02 , but in individuals with psoriasis it was 46.42 ± 57.2 . To ensure sufficient statistical power with a significance level of 5%, the present investigation requires a sample size of 40 patients, assuming identical observations will be made. Patients

coming to dermatology OPD in our institution which is an academic tertiary care hospital, with psoriasis were screened and after applying the exclusion criteria, eligible participants were recruited. This study was done between April 2023 and December 2023. Informed written consent was obtained.

Outcomes and Measures: After acquiring informed consent, a comprehensive history was gathered, which included demographic information, primary complaints, the onset and duration of the disease, as well as any related medical conditions or other skin problems. This information was carefully documented. An extensive inspection of the skin lesions caused by psoriasis was conducted, and the observations were recorded. The severity of the disease was assessed by calculating the Psoriasis Area Severity Index (PASI). A nail inspection was conducted. A comprehensive physical examination was conducted to identify any further abnormalities in other parts of the body. A fasting lipid profile and other pertinent investigations were done. Additionally, LAP, VAI, and PAI indices were computed using the appropriate formulas and results were recorded. All relevant information were included in a proforma. Photographs of the skin lesions were captured for clinical purposes.

Statistical Analysis: The statistical tool SPSS IBM version 26.0 will be utilized for data analysis. The normality assumption of all continuous variables will be assessed using the appropriate statistical test. Descriptive statistics, including the mean, standard deviation (SD), and range, will be computed. A bivariate correlation analysis will be conducted for all the variables under examination. ROC analysis will be conducted to determine the cutoff value of LAP index, VAI, and PAI in psoriasis patients. Additionally, logistic regression will be conducted. A two-sided probability with a P value less than 0.05 will be deemed statistically significant for all statistical tests.

Results

Demography: 40 patients with psoriasis were included in the study. 18 (45%) were males and 22 (55%) were females. The mean (SD) age of the patients was $44.77 (7.02)$. Table 1 displays the baseline data for all research participants.

Visceral fat Markers: In psoriasis patients, mean (SD) LAP was $190.82 (94.21)$, VAI was $5.16 (1.59)$ and PAI was $0.48 (0.14)$. Table 2 represents the comparison of LAP index, VAI and PAI across psoriasis patients with mild illness ($PASI \leq 10$) and those with moderate-to-severe illness ($PASI > 10$). The LAP index showed a statistically significant increase ($P = 0.0065$) in the moderate-to-severe psoriasis group (230.21 ± 91.1) compared to the mild psoriasis group (151.43 ± 81.56). Figure 1

depicts the link between the Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) and the LAP index in individuals with psoriasis. There was negligible link observed between the severity of psoriasis, as

measured by the Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI), and the LAP index within the psoriasis group, as determined by Pearson's correlation coefficient ($r=0.12$).

Table 1: Demographic characteristics

S No	Value	Mean	St Dev
1	Age (years)	44.77	7.02
2	Sex (M:F)	18:22	
3	BMI	24.56	2.59
4	Waist circumference	86.28	6.22
5	Triglycerides	138.4	50.31
6	HDL	42.52	8.01
7	PASI	11.05	4.59

Table 2: Comparison of LAP index, VAI and PAI among psoriasis patients

S No	Value	PASI ≤ 10		PASI >10		P value
		Mean	St. Dev	Mean	St. Dev	
1	LAP	151.43	81.56	230.21	91.1	0.006
2	VAI	5.006	1.67	5.32	1.5	0.54
3	PAI	0.46	0.16	0.43	0.3	0.27
4	BMI	23.305	2.14	25.815	2.4	0.0014
5	Waist circumference	83.4	5.49	89.15	5.65	0.002
6	Triglycerides	122.1	51.04	154.8	45.04	0.03

Figure 1: Correlation between the Psoriasis Area and Severity Index(PASI) and the LAP index

Figure 2: Psoriatic lesions over both forearm in a 55 yr. old female patient

Figure 3: Psoriatic lesions involving the back of a 56 yr. old male patient

Discussion

Psoriasis is an immune-mediated chronic inflammatory disease that often occurs alongside other health conditions. It is observed in around 0.5%–4.7% of population in the world. Psoriasis, a skin disease, has been linked to various metabolic ab-

normalities including obesity, dyslipidaemia, high blood pressure, resistance to insulin, and metabolic syndrome. [13]

Nevertheless, little research has been done on central adiposity in psoriasis patients, despite its link to higher cardiovascular morbidity. This aspect be-

comes more significant in the Indian context, where obesity has reached epidemic levels. Therefore, this study was conducted to examine the correlation between central obesity and psoriasis by utilizing the LAP index as a measure of central obesity.

Epidemiological evidence in psoriasis is growing, indicating that patients with psoriasis may have higher adiposity compared to individuals without the condition. [14] While the specific mechanisms behind this connection are currently not well understood, scientists have proposed that the release of pro-inflammatory substances by adipocytes may exacerbate psoriasis. Therefore, it appears that there is a significant overlap in the immunological pathways between psoriasis and obesity.

In our study, mean BMI, waist circumference and triglycerides were found to be significantly lesser in patients with PASI less than 10. This was similar to previous study conducted by Lindegard et al. [15] in Sweden with 159,200 participants over a span of 10 years, exploring the connection between psoriasis and obesity. The study revealed a correlation between women who have psoriasis and obesity. In 1995, another study conducted by Henseler et al. [16] using a registry that had 42,461 individuals. Among these individuals, 2,941 (7%) were diagnosed with psoriasis. The study revealed a notable increase in the occurrence of obesity among patients with psoriasis. Recent case-control research by Naldi et al. [17] involving 560 people who had psoriasis revealed that the likelihood of developing psoriasis was higher in those who were overweight (BMI 26-29) or obese (BMI \geq 30) compared to individuals with a normal weight. The odds ratio for psoriasis in the overweight group was 1.6, while in the obese group it was 1.9. A different study by Chiricozzi et al [18], based on registries, examined 127,706 individuals with mild psoriasis who were not undergoing systemic therapy or phototherapy, as well as 3,854 individuals with severe psoriasis who were receiving systemic therapy or phototherapy. The study found that those with severe psoriasis had a higher risk of obesity (odds ratio [OR] of 1.8) compared to those with mild psoriasis (OR of 1.3). Another research by Gottlieb et al. [19] discovered similar results in a study including 16,851 patients with psoriasis. The study revealed that patients under the age of 35 had a higher likelihood of being overweight (odds ratio [OR] of 2.2) compared to those above the age of 65 (OR of 1.6) when compared to healthy individuals. Thus, it appears that the correlation among psoriasis with obesity has been definitively proven.

There are multiple pathways that can help explain the connection among psoriasis and obesity. Individuals diagnosed with psoriasis are more prone to experiencing elevated risks of social isolation, unhealthy dietary patterns, depression, reduced physical activity, and heightened alcohol usage. [20] A

previous research revealed that those with psoriasis had a notably higher intake of fat, saturated fat, and alcohol in comparison to those without the condition. In addition, obese patients suffering from psoriasis engage in less physical activity compared to obese persons who do not have psoriasis. The shared chronic inflammatory condition may contribute to the heightened risk of psoriasis in obese patients. Adipose tissue serves as a highly efficient organ for storing lipids in the body, while also offering mechanical protection and insulation. [21] Obesity is the condition when white adipose tissue expands, resulting in the increased release of free fatty acids from white adipocytes. This, in turn, leads to raised levels of fatty acids in the bloodstream. Undoubtedly, the disruption induced by obesity plays a crucial role in the development of several disorders associated with obesity, such as psoriasis. [22]

The relationship between visceral fat with psoriasis has been documented, albeit the measurement of visceral fat in these investigations was conducted using CT scans and a body composition analyzer. [23] Due to the need for technological skills and costly equipment, these analytical methodologies cannot be utilized for everyday clinical treatment, especially in a nation such as India. Therefore, the LAP index, which can be readily determined using anthropometry and basic laboratory testing, is a more valuable tool in routine clinical practice.

Our study revealed a notable increase in the LAP index among psoriasis patients with a PASI score greater than 10, as opposed to those with a PASI score of 10 or lower. This suggests that psoriasis patients requiring systemic therapy have a significantly higher amount of visceral fat compared to those who can be effectively treated with topical therapy. Unfortunately, we were unable to discover any connection between the LAP index and PASI, therefore failing to establish a cause-and-effect relationship between the severity of psoriasis and visceral adiposity. The results align with the findings of the Turkish study, which did not establish a correlation between PASI and visceral fat rating. Previous investigations have established a causal relationship between PASI and obesity, although the specific connection to visceral obesity has not been proven. [24] Insulin resistance has been demonstrated as the causal connection between obesity and psoriasis. Therefore, our findings suggest that while a greater degree of visceral fat is linked to a more severe manifestation of psoriasis, this association is not strictly linear. This discovery becomes more significant in patients with a PASI score greater than 10, since they have a larger likelihood of experiencing severe visceral obesity and are at a heightened risk of developing cardiovascular illnesses.

In our study, mean (SD) age of the patients was

44.77 (7.02), BMI was 24.56 (2.59), Waist circumference was 86.28 (6.22), VAI was 5.16 (1.59) and PAI was 0.48 (0.14). This was similar to previous study by Ganguly et al. [25] which showed a mean age of 44.83 (12.83), BMI 24.12 (3.48), waist circumference 86.47 (8.9). Another study by Ataseven et al. [12] showed similar results with mean(SD) age of 43.5 (16.8) years, 66.1% patients overweight, PAI 0.5 (0.3). VAI was lower than our study with mean (range) 2.3 (0.4-18.1).

Nevertheless, our study does have certain limitations. The study was done using a modest sample size and used a cross-sectional design. Additionally, our study was not specifically designed to determine the causal relationship between obesity and severe psoriasis. Therefore, additional extensive epidemiological investigations are required to validate the correlation between the LAP index, VAI and PAI and psoriasis.

Conclusion

Our study shows a correlation between a high LAP index, PAI and VAI and psoriasis, therefore connecting visceral fat with psoriasis. Therefore, assessing visceral fat in patients with psoriasis can assist in identifying a larger number of individuals who are at a heightened risk of cardiovascular complications, even among those patients whose body mass index and waist circumference fall within the normal range. Consequently, it is recommended to regularly assess the LAP index in all patients with psoriasis, particularly those with a PASI score more than 10, in order to promptly detect and address the risk of cardiovascular disease.

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